

Are We the Plague for Nature?

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The Plague by the existentialist thinker Albert Camus is a powerful and prophetic novel about a plague epidemic in the large Algerian city of Oran. Published in French in 1947 as *La Peste* and in English in 1948, as *The Plague*, it is set sometime in the 1940s. The author doesn't provide an exact year, but he describes in vivid detail the pain and suffering that strikes the lives of rich and poor alike.

The Story

In April, thousands of rats stagger into the open and die. When a mild hysteria grips the population, the newspapers begin clamoring for action. The authorities finally arrange for the daily collection and cremation of the rats. Soon thereafter, M. Michel, the concierge for the building where Dr. Rieux works, dies after falling ill with a strange fever. When a cluster of similar cases appears, Dr. Rieux's friend, Castel, becomes certain that the illness is the bubonic plague. He and Dr. Rieux are forced to confront the indifference and denial of the authorities and other doctors in their attempts to urge quick, decisive action. Only after it becomes impossible to deny the serious epidemic, do the

authorities enact strict sanitation measures, placing the whole city under quarantine.

The Reaction

The public reacts to their sudden imprisonment with intense longing for absent loved ones. They indulge in selfish personal distress, convinced that their pain is unique in comparison to common suffering. The Jesuit priest Paneloux delivers a

stern sermon, declaring that the plague is God's punishment for Oran's sins. Raymond Rambert attempts to escape Oran to rejoin his wife in Paris, but the city's bureaucrats refuse to let him leave. He tries to escape by illegal means with the help of Cottard's criminal associates. Meanwhile, Rieux, Tarrou, and Grand doggedly battle the death and suffering wrought by the plague. Rambert finalizes his escape plan, but, after Tarrou tells him that Rieux is likewise separated from his wife, Rambert is ashamed to flee. He chooses to stay behind and help fight the epidemic. Cottard had committed an (undisclosed) crime in the past, so he has lived in constant fear of arrest and punishment. So he greets the plague epidemic with open arms because he no longer feels alone in his fearful suffering. Further, accumulates a great deal of wealth as a smuggler during the epidemic.

After several months, many of Oran's citizens lose their selfish obsession with personal suffering. They come to recognize the plague as a collective disaster that is everyone's concern. They confront their social responsibility and join the anti-plague efforts. When M. Othon's small son suffers a prolonged, excruciating death from the plague, Dr. Rieux shouts at Paneloux that he was an innocent victim. Paneloux, deeply shaken by the boy's death, delivers a second sermon that modifies the first. He declares that the inexplicable deaths of innocents force the Christian to choose

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between believing everything and believing nothing about God. When he falls ill, he refuses to consult a doctor, leaving his fate entirely in the hands of divine Providence. He dies clutching his crucifix, but the symptoms of his illness do not match those of the plague. Dr. Rieux records him as a “doubtful case.”

When the epidemic ends, Cottard cannot cope with the intensity of suffering. So he begins randomly firing his gun into the street until he is captured by the police. Grand, having recovered from a bout of plague, vows to make a fresh start in life. Tarrou dies just as the epidemic is waning, but he battles with all his strength for his life, just as he helped Rieux battle for the lives of others. Rambert's wife joins him in Oran after the city gates are finally opened, but Dr. Rieux's own wife dies of a prolonged illness before she and her husband can be reunited. The public quickly returns to its old routine, but Rieux knows that the battle against the plague is never over because the bacillus microbe can lie dormant for years. *The Plague* is his chronicle of the scene of human suffering that all too many people are willing to forget.

The Plot

The Plague isn't exactly a novel. It does not have a complex plot and dramatic action, though it has momentum and suspense. It's a philosophical work with reflections on freedom, terror, love, and exile and on the necessity of bearing witness. Still, despite its refusal to play by the traditional rules of French fiction, it offers six major characters, all of them men and all intended to be representative types, though they lack real individuality.

The six men are: Bernard Rieux, a medical doctor; Jean Tarrou, an outsider who arrives in Oran just before the advent of the plague; Raymond Rambert, a journalist; Joseph Grand, a government clerk; Monsieur Cottard who goes mad and shoots people on the street; and Father Paneloux, a Jesuit priest. There

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are no political leaders and no military officers. Indeed, there's a vacuum of leadership.

The Religious Approach

The Plague offers a happy ending of sorts. The pestilence vanishes almost as mysteriously as it arrived. Optimism is reborn, but a sense of uncertainty lingers. Those who are alive in Oran want medals merely for surviving. The reader is left with the assumption that the plague can return at any time. On the last page, Camus writes about "the never ending fight against terror."

His language suggest that he was thinking about religion when he wrote *The Plague*, and, though it's not an explicitly Christian book, it offers words and concepts like "grace," "crucifixion" and "deliverance." Religion provides a kind of subtext, though the book doesn't endorse Oran's Catholic Church. What Camus wants are healers, not priests, political leaders and certainly not demagogues.

At the height of the plague, when five hundred people a week are dying, the Catholic priest Paneloux explains the plague as god's punishment for depravity.

But Camus's hero Dr Rieux loathes this approach. The plague is not a punishment for anything deserved. That would be to imagine that the universe was moral or had some sort of design to it. But Dr Rieux watches a young innocent child die in his hospital and knows better: suffering is entirely randomly distributed, it makes no sense, it is no ethical force, it is simply absurd and that is the kindest thing one can say of it.

**"If all insects on Earth disappeared, within 50 years all life on Earth would end. If all human beings disappeared from the Earth, within 50 years all forms of life would flourish."
Jonas Salk**

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The doctor works tirelessly against death, he tries to lessen the suffering of those around him. But he is no saint. In one of the most central lines of the book, Camus writes: "This whole thing is not about heroism. It's about decency. It may seem a ridiculous idea, but the only way to fight the plague is with decency." A character asks Rieux what decency is. Doctor Rieux's response is as clipped as it is eloquent: 'In general, I can't say, but in my case I know that it consists in doing my job.'

Camus' Doctor Rieux appreciates dancing, love and nature; he is hugely sensitive to the smell of flowers, to the colours at sunset and – like Camus – adores swimming in the sea, slipping out after an evening on the wards to surrender himself to the reassuring immensity of the waves.

The Pest of War

Camus equates pestilence with war and says that both are horrible. "There have been many plagues in the world as there have been wars, yet plagues and wars always find people equally unprepared. [...] When a war breaks out people say: 'It won't last, it's too stupid.' And war is certainly too stupid, but that doesn't prevent it from lasting. Stupidity always carries doggedly on, as people would notice if they were not always thinking about themselves. In this respect, the citizens of Oran were like the rest of the world, they thought about themselves, in other words, they were humanists: they did not believe in pestilence. A pestilence does not have human dimensions, so people tell themselves that it is unreal, that it is a bad dream which will end. But it does not always end and, from one bad dream to the next, it is people who end, humanists first of all because they have not prepared themselves."

Humans Being as Plague?

But he has not equated human being with plague. Considering the harm that we do to the other living species, that is exactly what the environmental activist and television presenter Sir David Attenborough has said. Humans are a plague on the Earth that need to be controlled by limiting population growth. He added that humans are threatening their own existence and that of other species by using up the world's resources. The discoverer and developer of the first successful polio vaccine, Jonas Salk, supposedly claimed: "If all insects on Earth disappeared, within 50 years all life on Earth would end. If all human beings disappeared from the Earth, within 50 years all forms of life would flourish" (Cited in Attenborough 2013).

Reference

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